

TRANSFORMATION IN EDUCATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7582694>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 18th January 2023

Accepted: 27th January 2023

Online: 28th January 2023

KEY WORDS

Transformation, distance education, virtual educational systems, innovations, education development strategies.

ABSTRACT

Identification of the reasons for the transformation of education is important for developing the right strategy for the development of education in Uzbekistan.

Visible trends suggest that the current stage is a transitional one. Comparison of classical, distance and virtual learning systems is carried out. The roles, tasks and results of the activities of the participants in the learning process are defined.

Humanity is always faced with the need to provide a more efficient way of preserving and transferring knowledge. Many contradictions generated by modern post-industrial culture [1] allow us to assert that the current stage of social dynamics is transitional and will last for several decades. The processes taking place in education are the result of changes in the economy, culture, politics, and they are also transitional. Understanding the causes, trends and prospects of these transformations will allow us to build practical activities focused on leadership in the field of education.

Let us dwell on the assessment of modern trends in the classical system of education. In general, it has not changed very much since the time when Aristotle taught at the Athenian Lycus. The teacher acts as a translator of knowledge, the student must concentrate and understand the information presented. The interaction happens synchronously. The task of the teacher is not only to transfer certain information, but also to create a "friendly" feedback channel - to assess the effectiveness of learning information by the trainee. The learning algorithm is based on the presentation of the material by the teacher, accompanying it with visual demonstrations and consolidating the understanding achieved by solving practical problems by the trainee.

Printed materials, educational and methodical sets of literature and assignments are used. The time and place of the classes are fixed. The results are assessed by the student's knowledge of the material presented by the teacher, the ability to solve practical problems on the topic and the experience and skills to solve problematic issues on the topic.

The modern education system should provide society with a confident transition to the digital age, aimed at increasing productivity, new types of labor, human needs, which can be done by including all segments of the population in the education process, building individual learning routes, managing your learning outcomes, virtual and augmented reality. Digital resources that are used today in everyday human activities, make it possible to overcome the

barriers of conventional learning: the rate of mastering the program, the choice of a teacher, forms and methods of teaching. At the same time, digital technologies lead to the emergence of many new problems at the level of countries and companies that are associated with digital security and the development of digital literacy, with changes in the requirements for the competencies of specialists and the labor market as a whole, with the problem of extracting knowledge and meanings from a large data stream, as well as the ability to apply this new knowledge in practice [2].

The modern world has moved to the next level of development of new technologies - digitalization, i.e. the era of big data and technologies based on them. In education, digitalization is aimed at ensuring the continuity of the learning process - lifelong learning (life-long-learning), as well as its individualization based on advanced learning technologies (advanced-learning-technologies) [3].

In the context of the accelerated development of the economy of Uzbekistan, special requirements are set for the training of highly qualified personnel.

The Ministry of Higher and Secondary Specialized Education, together with the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations, has taken measures to forecast the need for personnel in the real sector of the economy at least 10–15 years in advance and, based on this, train them [4].

The main prospect of the transformation taking place in education is the emergence, development and implementation of VR (Virtual Reality) systems in the learning process. Let us single out the circle of the main problems arising from this conclusion.

The main problem is a lack of understanding of the depth of what is happening in the scientific community. Therefore, until now, the main attention is paid to the development and implementation of DL. The accompanying processes associated with the development of distance courses and technical support take up significant human, material, informational, legal and other resources.

Meanwhile, these developments will soon, in our opinion, become obsolete and will require not just an update, but a fundamentally high-quality replacement. All this is fraught not only with financial losses; the most dangerous in this case is the problem of loss of time and strategic advantage.

The rapid development of VR systems in education will allow achieving a number of strategic results, among which the main one is the technological advance of competitors. It is the development of VR technologies that should be devoted today to developments in the field of ensuring the quality of education. First of all, these are technical and software technologies for creating VR.

The next large-scale task is the development of systems for assessing the cognitive and motivational psychological state of the student [5; 6], the creation of mathematical models of the state of a student, the means of technical and software implementation of assessment systems, the study of their psychological validity [7]. The third major task is to change pedagogical technologies and methods, as well as to train teachers for mentors who are ready to work in fundamentally new conditions and play non-traditional roles. The education system implements the mission of preserving and retransmitting cultural values, it is inherently conservative and cannot be otherwise.

In order for its radical transformation to become possible, it is necessary to educate a new generation.

Uzbekistan, as one of the few developing countries, has absolute adult literacy rates (100% in 2022) compared to other countries with similar levels of GDP per capita.

Along with countries that actively implement and use new technologies, there are entire regions that are cut off from global information communications and do not use the advantages that allow them to switch to a new type of functioning of the economic system.

Among the prerequisites for the development of the digital economy in Uzbekistan, several aspects can be distinguished [8].

Firstly, the national education system has a high potential for training specialists in the digital economy.

Secondly, there are original organizational and technological solutions for creating an effective infrastructure for the digital economy.

Thirdly, the integration and development of specific cases based on modern principles of the digital economy will create a synergistic effect and lead to the overall growth of the economy of Uzbekistan.

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